

Association study between D₂ receptor A-241G, rs1799978 genetic variation and olanzapine efficacy in Iraqi schizophrenic patients

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Received 1 September 2023 ♦ Accepted 12 October 2023 ♦ Published 29 January 2024

Citation: Al-Musawi ZJMA, Al-Juhaishi AMR (2024) Association study between D₂ receptor A-241G, rs1799978 genetic variation and olanzapine efficacy in Iraqi schizophrenic patients. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e111984>

Abstract

This study aimed to assess the role of D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) genetic polymorphism and olanzapine response and safety in Iraqi schizophrenic patients. The case-control study composed of 100 schizophrenic patients consisting of both genders were recruited from the Psychiatry Outpatient Department and 50 apparently healthy volunteers, served as a control group. Patient response to olanzapine was evaluated with the aiding of the PANSS and genotyping of D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) polymorphisms was detected using the nested PCR method. The heterozygous (AG) and mutant (GG) alleles of D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) were significantly predominated in schizophrenic patients and absent in healthy volunteers. Schizophrenic patients with the G allele of D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) and who were administered olanzapine exhibited a notable resistance to olanzapine. In conclusion, the genetic polymorphism of D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) was significantly associated with resistance to olanzapine in Iraqi schizophrenic patients.

Keywords

Olanzapine, D₂ receptor, Schizophrenia, genetic polymorphism

Introduction

One percent of people worldwide suffer from schizophrenia, a serious mental condition, and 0.24 to 4.7% of persons in the Arab countries. Schizophrenia is the most prevalent psychiatric condition in Iraq, with prevalence increasing from 12% in 2000 to 15% in 2020 (Ahmed 2022). Effective antipsychotic medications primarily block dopamine (D₂) receptors, which is in line with the pathophysiology of schizophrenia (Carli et al. 2021). Atypical antipsychotic drugs are successful at treating both schizophrenia's positive and negative symptoms. They have proven effective in treating resistant forms of schizophrenia and have a lower risk of developing extrapyramidal symptoms (EPS) and

other movement disorders, like parkinsonism, akathisia, dystonia, and tardive dyskinesia, which are linked to physical impairment and subjective discomfort and distress (Li et al. 2016). Olanzapine is an atypical antipsychotic drug that is frequently prescribed. It inhibits dopamine action at the post-synaptic receptor in the mesolimbic pathway, specifically at the D₂ receptors, by binding loosely to these receptors and readily dissociating, allowing normal dopamine neurotransmission to take place. As a result, it causes a decrease in the pleasant symptoms that patients experience, such as delusions, hallucinations, and slurred speech, cognition, and behavior (Grinchii and Dremencov 2020). Pharmacogenetic biomarkers seek to identify patients who may benefit from specific medications based

on genetic variations. This approach may allow for the improvement of antipsychotic agent treatment and multiple ineffective trials and the deterioration brought on by the lack of response could be avoided by early detection of patients who are resistant to treatment. In the treatment of psychiatric diseases other than schizophrenia, olanzapine has been widely used. Treatment-resistant psychoses typically require the physician to either change to a different monotherapy or add to the current strategy to increase the pharmacological profile without identifying the causes of resistance. As a result, patients are exposed to additional unfavorable side effects (Toto et al. 2019). Four studies on patients of Han-Chinese, Japanese, African American, and Thai descent reported conflicting results on the association between the A-241G (rs1799978) polymorphism and the risperidone response (Xing et al. 2007; Nuntamool et al. 2017). Investigations of the responsiveness to antipsychotic medication in Mexican patients with D₂ receptor A-241G genes for schizophrenia showed that patients with treatment resistance had a higher prevalence of the G allele (Escamilla et al. 2018). The aim of this study was to investigate the responsiveness of olanzapine and their associated with D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) gene polymorphism in Iraqi schizophrenic patients.

Subjects, materials and methods

Subjects

The adult-aged patients or older of both genders were estimated for competence. Schizophrenic patients diagnosed based on the DSM-IV (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) (Tandon et al. 2013). After completing a written consent form that contained a full explanation of the study's objective and a request to complete a specially created questionnaire, all participants were enrolled in the study. Patients were receiving 10 mg/day olanzapine from 6 months up to years with no additional disorder were included in this study. Patients with previous hyperglycemia/diabetes, hypotension, weight gain, hyperprolactinemia, tardive dyskinesia before taking olanzapine or receiving treatment or any other medicine that interacts with olanzapine such as bromocriptine, levodopa, methylodopa were excluded from the study.

Study design

The case-control study was performed from December 2022 to April 2023 in Al-Hassan Al-Mojtaba hospital. The 100 patients consisting of both male and female, aged between 20 and 65 years were recruited from Psychiatry Outpatient Department and 50 apparently healthy without any disease comprising both males and females aged 20 to 63 years, were also enrolled, and served as a control group. The study was approved by the scientific and ethical committee, Kerbala University, college of pharmacy

and Ministry of Health of Iraq- Kerbala health department with the project being assigned No: 244.

Evaluation the patient response to olanzapine

The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS), which has three parts: Positive (P), Negative (N), and cognitive or General Psychopathology (G) was utilized by the psychiatrist to gauge the illness's severity and the patient's reaction to olanzapine. The General Psychopathology subscale has 16 items with a strong focus on cognition (G1–G16), while the Positive and Negative subscales each have seven items (P1–P7, N1–N7). This information is shown in Table 1. Each component is given a score between 1 and 7 according to severity, with 1 denoting absence, 2; minimum, 3; mild, 4; moderate, 5; moderate-severity, 6; severity, and 7; extremeness. A thorough definition and exact standards for each of the seven rating points are provided for each item on the PANSS. The minimum scores required by this scoring approach are 7 points for each of the Positive and Negative subscales and the cognitive symptoms had 16 points, for a total of at least 30 points. Positive, Negative, and Cognition each have maximum scores of 49, 49, and 112 points, respectively, for a combined maximum score of 210 points (Shankar and Nate 2007).

Table 1. Positive and negative syndrome scale (PANSS).

Positive (P)	Negative (N)	Cognitive psychopathology (G)
P1 Delusions	N1 Blunted affect	G1 Somatic concern
P2 Conceptual disorganization	N2 Emotional withdrawal	G2 Anxiety
P3 Hallucinatory behavior	N3 Poor rapport	G3 Guilt feelings
P4 Excitement	N4 passive/apathetic social withdrawal	G4 Tension
P5 Grandiosity	N5 Difficulty in abstract thinking	G5 Mannerism and posturing
P6 Suspiciousness/persecution	N6 Lack of spontaneity and flow of conversation	G6 Depression
P7 Hostility	N7 Stereotyped thinking	G7 Motor retardation
		G8 Uncooperativeness
		G9 Unusual thought content
		G10 Disorientation
		G11 Poor attention
		G12 lack of judgment and insight
		G13 Disturbing of volition
		G14 Poor impulse control
		G15 Preoccupation
		G16 Active social avoidance

Positive syndrome is characterized by symptoms like hallucinations, delusions, and disorganized thought. Cognitive, affective, and social deficiencies, such as deflection of emotion and passive disinterest, are characteristics of the negative syndrome. Many cognitive problems, including confusion, inadequate attention, inability to understand, and purposeful avoiding of people, make up general psychopathology.

Genotyping for D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) polymorphisms detection

The genomic DNA was purified from 2 ml whole blood taken from schizophrenic patients and healthy volunteers using the phenol/chloroform method. According to a previous study, the genotyping for D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) polymorphisms was detected using the a two-step nested polymerase chain reaction (PCR) (Zahari et al. 2011). The procedure used an overall volume of 25.0 L, contained 200 ng of DNA template, 1.0 mM MgCl₂, 0.2 mM dNTPs (Promega, Madison, Wisconsin, USA), 0.5 U of Biotool DNA Taq Polymerase (B&M Labs, Madrid, Spain), and 1 Biotool PCR buffer (B&M Labs, Madrid, Spain), and produced equal amplification of all alleles. The concentrations of the best primer (Invitrogen, California, USA) were discovered to be 0.15 to 0.40 M. Standard 0.2 mL Eppendorf PCR tubes were used for all PCRs, which were then run through an Eppendorf Mastercycler Gradient Cyler (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The initial PCR amplified a section of DRD2 from exons 3 to 4. Prior to the cycling program, at first, The DNA was denatured for two minutes at 94 °C. Thereafter, a total of 35 cycles of DNA annealing at 65 °C for one minute, extension at 72 °C for two minutes, and a final extension session at 72 °C for five minutes were carried out. To examine the PCR data, a 2.0% agarose gel (LE, analytical grade; Promega, Madison, Wisconsin, USA) stained in ethidium bromide in a 1 Tris-borate-EDTA (TBE) buffer was utilized. This process took 90 minutes at 130 V. The first PCR, which employed the primer sets, produced 276 bp-sized fragments. After the first PCR was successful, 2.0 L of the diluted PCR output was utilized as a template for a second PCR to identify wild-type or mutant alleles. The reaction mixture used for the second PCR was the same as the one used for the first. The second PCR consisted of 15 cycles with DNA being denatured for 1 minute at 94 °C, annealed for 1 minute at 63 °C, and extended for 2 minutes at 72 °C. Following that, a 2.0% agarose gel and 1 TBE were used to analyze 10 mL of the second PCR result for 90 minutes at 130 V. The predicted fragment size of the products is 252 bp. The PCR primers sequence used for detection of the D₂ receptor gene A-241G (rs 1799978) were illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Primer sequence of D2 receptor A-241G (rs 1799978).

Primer	Sequence	Product Size (bp)
(A-241G rs 1799978)	Forward1 5- ACTGGCGAGCAGACGGTGA -3	252 bp
	Reverse1 5- TGAAGCTGGACAGCTCTGC -3	
	Forwad2 5- CAGCTGCAATCACAGCTTA -3	
	Reverse2 5- CAGCTGCAATCACAGCTTG-3	

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis will be performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 26). Descriptive statistics for the numerical data were present as the mean

and standard error of the mean (Mean ± SEM) and the non-numerical data were number and %. The normal distribution of data was tested with the aid of Shapiro – Wilk test. Numerical data will be analyzed by using an independent sample T-test and a one-way ANOVA-post-hoc-LSD test. Non-numerical data will be analyzed by using the Chi-square test. The multinomial logistic regression was used to assess the association of genetic variation with efficacy of olanzapine. The P values less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic data

The demographic data including age, gender, and BMI were assessed in both healthy and schizophrenia volunteers. In terms of age and gender, there were no real distinctions ($P > 0.05$) between the healthy volunteers and those with schizophrenia as show in Table 3. Schizophrenic patients demonstrated significant weight gain, as evidenced by increased BMI 29.11 ± 0.64 in schizophrenic males and 30.01 ± 0.81 in schizophrenic females compared to the healthy individuals 24.52 ± 0.57 in males and 24.89 ± 0.69 in females ($P < 0.05$) as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Demographic data of both healthy and schizophrenic volunteers (data present as mean ± S.E and No (%)).

Variables	Volunteer		P – value
	Healthy (n = 50)	Schizophrenic (n = 100)	
Age (y)	38.98 ± 1.73	39.11 ± 1.44	0.256
Gender	Male	32 (64%)	0.190
	Female	55 (55%)	
BMI (kg/m ²)	Male	24.52 ± 0.57	<0.0001*
	Female	24.89 ± 0.69	

*: Significant effect ($P < 0.05$) compared to healthy group.

Prevalence of D₂ receptor genes A-241G (rs1799978)

The results of genotype D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) genetic polymorphism showed a clear band with a molecular size 252 bps as presented in Fig. 1. The wild allele (AA) was predominated (100%) in healthy volunteers and about (78%) in schizophrenic patient, while the heterozygous type (AG) and mutant type (GG) were only presented in schizophrenic individuals with ratio of 14% and 8% respectively as shown in Fig. 2. The frequencies of the D₂ receptor alleles rs1799978 (A-241G) were significantly different between the healthy and schizophrenic volunteers ($P < 0.05$) as show in Table 4. There were significantly difference among male gender of healthy and schizophrenic individuals and There were no significantly difference among female gender of healthy and schizophrenic individuals regarding three different alleles of rs1799978 (A-241G) ($P > 0.05$) as explained in Tables 5, 6 and Fig. 3.

Figure 1. Genotyping of D₂ receptor genes A-241G (rs1799978).

Figure 2. The Prevalence of D₂ receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) among volunteers.

Table 4. The Prevalence of D₂ receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) among volunteers (data present as No (%)).

Volunteers	Alleles of rs1799978 (A-241G)			P - Value
	AA	AG	GG	
Healthy	50 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0.002*
Schizophrenic	78 (75%)	14 (14%)	8 (8%)	

*: Significant effect (P < 0.05) between all groups.

Effects of D₂ receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) on PANSS

The schizophrenic symptoms were represented by PANSS score which was significantly high in schizophrenic

Table 5. The Prevalence of D₂ receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) among male volunteers (data present as No (%)).

Male volunteers	Alleles of rs1799978 (A-241G)			P - Value
	AA	AG	GG	
Healthy	32 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0.037*
Schizophrenic	45 (81.8%)	4 (7.3%)	6 (10.9%)	

*: Significant effect (P < 0.05) between all groups.

Table 6. The Prevalence of D₂ Receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) among female volunteers (data present as No (%)).

Female volunteers	Alleles of rs1799978 (A-241G)			P - Value
	AA	AG	GG	
Healthy	18 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0.052
Schizophrenic	33 (73.4%)	10 (22.2%)	2 (4.4%)	

patients who taken olanzapine and had either heterozygous (AG) allele 146.93 ± 4.91 or mutant (GG) allele 197.13 ± 4.07 of A-241G (rs1799978) as compared to those with wild (AA) allele 70.54 ± 2.46 ($P < 0.05$) as shown in Table 7. There were significantly difference among schizophrenic volunteers who carried heterozygous (AG) allele and mutant (GG) allele of A-241G (rs1799978) regarding the PANSS score ($P < 0.05$) as shown in Table 7 and Fig. 4. There were significantly associated between response of schizophrenic patient according to PANSS and G allele of A-241G (rs1799978) (95% CI = 7.098, 9.067) for patients carry heterozygous (AG) allele and (95% CI = 7.006, 9.237) for patients carry mutant (GG) allele ($P < 0.05$) as explained in Table 8.

Figure 3. The Prevalence of D₂ receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) among both male and female volunteers.

Table 7. The PANSS score of schizophrenic and healthy volunteers (data present as mean \pm S.E).

Variables	Volunteer			P-value	
	Healthy	Schizophrenic			
		AA	AG		GG
PANSS	30.24 \pm 0.32	70.54 \pm 2.46	146.93 \pm 4.91	197.13 \pm 4.07	<0.0001 ^a

^a: Significant effect (P < 0.05) among all study groups.

Figure 4. The PANSS score of schizophrenic and healthy volunteers.**Table 8.** The multinomial logistic regression of D₂ receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) and PANSS score.

Variable	Allele of A-241G	OR (95% CI)	P-value
PANSS	AA	1 [*]	
	AG	8.022 (7.098–9.067)	<0.0001 ^a
	GG	7.928 (7.006–9.237)	<0.0001 ^a

^a: significant effect (p < 0.05), OR: Odds Ratio, CI: Confidence interval, *: reference group.

Discussion

Although olanzapine is the most widely used atypical antipsychotic medication, it is also used to treat a variety of disorders including autism, schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and anorexia nervosa. Its resistance, which was brought on by some psychiatric disorders such as the negative symptoms of schizophrenia, may cause restrictions on use or the need to switch to another antipsychotic drug or add antidepressants, both of which may exacerbate unpleasant side effects (Leucht et al. 2009; Lang et al. 2023). Another clinical trial found that olanzapine did not improve the positive and negative symptoms in some patients with refractory schizophrenia after failure of typical or atypical antipsychotic agents (Lindenmayer et al. 2002). The exact mechanism of schizophrenia developed resistance to olanzapine remains unknown.

This study explained the present heterozygous (AG) and mutant (GG) alleles of D₂ receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) among both gender of Iraqi schizophrenic patients and not presented in healthy volunteers. The similar outcome was shown in Thai children and adolescents with autism, and this genetic variant displayed non-stable clinical symptom (Nuntamool et al. 2017). A Canadian study found that aggressive kids were more likely to have two copies of the G gene at A-241G (Zai et al. 2012). Another investigation found that the D₂ receptor allele A-241G (rs1799978) gene is encodes a high level of D₂ receptor, which may result

in inadequate risperidone blocking of these receptors and unstable clinical symptoms (Arinami et al. 1997).

In this study, the schizophrenic symptoms according PANSS score in patients with either heterozygous (AG) and mutant (GG) alleles of D₂ receptor alleles A-241G (rs1799978) and taken olanzapine were not significantly improved in comparison to those with wild (AA) allele. Numerous clinical research found that in the Han Chinese and Japanese populations, carriers of the AA allele of A-241G had greater PANSS score improvements and responses to antipsychotic medications than carriers of the AG and GG alleles (Ma et al. 2019). In relation to SNP A-241G, Ikeda et al. found relationships between the A allele and response and the G allele and absence of response (Ikeda et al. 2008). Another study found that a high dopamine concentration at the mesolimbic loop is linked to rapidly developing positive symptoms; as a result, people with the G allele of A-241G experience psychiatric symptoms, have poor responses to many antipsychotic medications, and need high doses of one or a combination of antipsychotic agents (Yamanaka et al. 2016). In contrast, a different study discovered that the D₂ receptor allele A-241G (rs1799978) genetic polymorphism was substantially related with olanzapine sensitivity, and G allele carriers demonstrated greater response to olanzapine compared to patients with wild AA (Yan et al. 2020).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the genetic polymorphism of D₂ receptor A-241G (rs1799978) was significantly associated with resistance to olanzapine in Iraqi schizophrenic patient.

Acknowledgments

This study was conducted in the Psychiatry Outpatient Department of Al-Hassan Al-Mojtaba hospital. Therefore, we extend our thanks and appreciation to all members of the said department, including nurses, service workers, resident doctors, and statistics employees.

Zahra Jawd Mohammed Ali: Conducted all experimental and analytical work and wrote the manuscript.; Atheer Majid Rashid Al-juhiashi: Provided supervision throughout the project and proofread the manuscript.

This research was undertaken without the support of any external funding agencies or grants. All costs associated with the design, execution, analysis, and manuscript preparation of this study were borne by the authors. We would like to acknowledge our institutional affiliations for providing the necessary infrastructure and resources that enabled the completion of this work, but no direct financial support was received. We are grateful for the internal resources and support that made this research possible.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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